
SOCIO-ECONOMIC FEATURES OF PUBLIC FINANCE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of public finance management. Public finance serves to ensure economic stability and development through the formation, distribution and effective management of funds. The study examines such important aspects as the state budget, fiscal policy, tax system and public debt management. It also analyzes advanced international experiences and proposes strategies that can be applied in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The article is aimed at developing effective management mechanisms for public finance and increasing its positive impact on economic growth.

Key words: Public finance, budget policy, fiscal management, tax system, public debt, economic stability.

Introduction.

Public finance management is an integral part of the country's financial system. Public finance management is the main area that coordinates the distribution process after the first gross distribution of the gross domestic product created in the country, which is considered an organic continuation of the production process. It is through public finance management that the turnover of production, services and work processes is ensured. Also, favorable conditions are created for the continuous financing of social entities. Proper organization of public finance management is one of the important factors in the rational and fair organization, development and improvement of financial relations.

Public finance management plays an important role in ensuring economic stability and social well-being. The country's fiscal policy, the processes of formation and distribution of budget funds are considered the main factors of economic growth. Public finance serves not only to balance budget revenues and expenditures, but also to ensure socio-economic development through the effective management of financial resources.

Today, many countries are striving to improve the efficiency of financial management by reforming their fiscal systems and improving tax and budget policies. International experience shows that transparency and efficiency of public finances have a positive impact on economic development. In this regard, improving the public finance management system, introducing modern

management methods and optimal allocation of financial resources are also important tasks in Uzbekistan.

Literature review

An analysis of scientific sources on public finance management shows that this area has been widely studied as one of the important factors of economic stability and development. The literature mainly examines such important areas as fiscal policy, the budget system, tax administration, and public debt.

Public finance represents economic relations related to providing centralized sources of financing for state and local sectors of the economy, the most important programs for the development of production and the social sector, organizations and institutions in the budgetary sphere, etc. Their activities are aimed at achieving the general goals of developing a socially oriented economy. [1].

Public finance is a set of economic relations arising in real money circulation in connection with the formation, distribution and use of centralized funds of financial resources. [2].

Violation of the law of proportional development of macroeconomics is manifested in certain types of macroeconomic imbalances. [3]:

a) structural crises (imbalance between the elementary composition of production and general needs);

b) economic crisis of overproduction (excess of the total volume of production over the total volume of payable needs);

v) mass unemployment (decrease in demand for labor relative to supply in the labor market);

g) inflation (the supply of money exceeds the demand for it).

The market economy is a complex and constantly evolving mechanism that reflects a self-regulating and self-developing system. In market conditions, both consumers and producers pursue only their own interests.

While representatives of the classical economic school emphasized the need to limit the role of the state in the economy, [4], Keynes justified the importance of fiscal policy by considering public finances as a means of stimulating economic activity [5]. Musgrave and Musgrave analyzed the functional areas of public finance and studied their impact on economic stability [6].

Research methodology

The main goal of the study is to improve the efficiency of public finance management, improve the budget system, optimize tax policy and study modern methods of managing public expenditures. The study analyzes scientific literature, international experience and theoretical approaches to public finance management. At this stage, the basic principles of financial policy, budget processes and theoretical aspects of the tax system are studied. Based on the results of the study, proposals are developed to improve public finance management. These include making budget processes more transparent, optimizing tax benefits, controlling public spending and effectively distributing financial resources.

Analysis and results.

The independent financial sector creates the finance of state-owned enterprises. Its emergence is associated with the development of the public sector in the economies of a number of Western European countries (Great Britain, France, Italy, Germany, Austria), and this process has become very widespread after World War II. Its main goal is to support the private economy by preserving and developing sectors of production that, due to their nature, have low profitability and are therefore unprofitable for business (railways, air transport, electricity, gas, coal industry, etc.), but are extremely important.

Thus, state-owned enterprises reflect an attempt to eliminate the conflict between the interests of private entrepreneurship and national economic problems. At the same time, the finance of state-owned enterprises is a link in state finance. Through it, the state participates in the primary distribution of national income, accumulates in its own hands part of the income generated by these

enterprises. State-owned enterprises have fixed and revolving funds assigned to them, operate according to an independent estimate, and carry out legally regulated interactions with the state budget. Depending on the type of enterprise, they have varying degrees of autonomy, production and financial independence.

As a special part of state finance, monetary relations that constitute the content of state credit are manifested. State credit relations arise in connection with the attraction of temporarily free funds of enterprises, organizations and the population and their timely transfer to state authorities to ensure the financing of state expenditures. State credit is a monetary relationship in which authorities and management bodies of all levels act as borrowers, creditors and guarantors. In state credit, these relations are associated with the attraction of temporarily free funds of enterprises, organizations and the population and their transfer to state authorities to finance state needs. In international credit, foreign states, their companies, firms, as well as international and interstate financial institutions enter into relations with each other.

In the structure of state finances, extra-budgetary funds form a separate link. The state budget allows for the attraction of funds, largely due to the fact that revenues are not assigned to specific types of expenses. However, it is impossible to achieve excessive attraction of funds on expenditure lines, in particular, social needs are of particular concern, since there is always a risk of reducing spending for these purposes. Therefore, it is extremely important to identify the most urgent areas for development, ensure the targeted allocation and use of incoming funds. This situation has become a serious basis for organizing the financing of targeted state tasks from appropriate extra-budgetary funds. Extra-budgetary funds have a strictly targeted task, autonomous management, and can be formed on the basis of specialization and allocation of specific expenses from the budget that are of great importance for a specific period, or on the basis of attaching private sources of income to funds. At the present stage of economic development, both methods are used. The purpose of the formation of extra-budgetary funds is to provide society with independent sources of income in addition to the budget for extremely important expenses. The budget deficit is also one of the important factors determining the expediency of the formation of extra-budgetary funds. The excess of budget expenses over revenues requires not only finding additional financial resources to cover it, but also redistributing funds received from enterprises, organizations, institutions and the population to cover certain types of expenses. The diversity of forms of ownership and management necessitates the need for redistribution of funds in society, along with budget methods.

Determining the principles of organization and functioning of public finance is an important methodological factor, which allows us to determine the directions of influence of finance on the development of state and local sectors of the economy, to develop criteria for their operation. State and local finance rely on information flows. The adoption of government decisions is based on a set of information. Analysis of incoming information is important both during decision-making and in monitoring the process of its implementation. This information is embodied in operational and statistical reports, contracts and agreements, accounting documents, etc. Public finance has a clearly targeted direction. They affect certain socio-political interests of individual segments of society. However, in all its aspects, they are aimed at solving state and local tasks. Public finance is an important link in the country's financial system, aimed at providing the state with the necessary funds to perform its economic, social and political functions. By its economic essence, public finance is a system of macroeconomic relations associated with the formation of monetary reserves at the disposal of the state in the process of distribution and redistribution of social product and national income and the use of these state monetary reserves for expenses on the development of expanded reproduction, to meet the growing socio-cultural needs of society, to meet the needs for financial support of the defense and management sectors.

Fig. 1: Public Finance Management Cycle

The specific nature of public finance is determined by the fact that the state itself appears as a participating subject in it. The economic essence of public finance is interpreted in various ways, and it includes separate interrelated links, each of which performs its own functions. The structure of public finance includes: budgetary relations formed at different levels of state administration, extra-budgetary funds, public credit relations, and the finances of state enterprises. With the help of the functional tasks of the above-mentioned state finance units, the state influences a wide range of economic and social processes and has the ability to solve sectoral and territorial problems.

The Public Accounting System (PAS) used by the government, System Application Product (SAP) facilitates all stages of the financial management cycle starting with planning and setting the budget framework, through to reporting and review of the outcome of the budget.

The Public Accounting System (PAS) gives a better, accurate and timely financial information as most of the government's financial transactions are recorded. It enables the government to publish financial reports and provides greater transparency of the financial information. It improves fiscal and financial management and provides better cash flow management through the Treasury Single Account (PBA), enabling the government to be more effective in maintaining financial discipline. It narrows down the chances for corruption and the access to accounting information provides opportunity for more informed financial and managerial decision making. The system has also helped in transition to proper book keeping and accounting through standard operating procedures and standards like International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS).

Public finance reflects the value distribution relations that include the formation of the state's total income and the direction of state expenditures. The budget is the main link in state finance. Because approximately 20-25% of GDP is redistributed through the budget. The state receives a large amount of monetary resources through the budget. With the help of such monetary resources, the state carries out its socio-economic, political and other tasks in society. As a result of financial redistribution using budgetary relations, a significant part of the national income is accumulated. As we noted above, the financial basis of the activities of central and local authorities is the state budget. The budget is an economic category, because its material basis is monetary income received as a result of social production. Therefore, in the process of organizing budgetary relations in any country, the interests of production must be taken into account. Through the budget, the state has

the opportunity to actively influence the economy. Because through the budget, a large amount of monetary resources of the economy are redistributed between sectors and regions. Therefore, in the process of forming budget revenues and using them for social needs, it regulates cash income and savings in all sectors and areas of the state, and has the ability to solve regional problems related to ensuring economic potential, investment activity and sustainable economic growth in various regions of the country.

Table 1. Characteristics of market and state regulators of the economy.

Market organizer	State organizer
Economic decisions (what, how, and for whom to produce) are made at the microeconomic level and in the interests of firms and households.	Management decisions are made at the macro level, taking into account national goals and interests.
Horizontal (cooperative) economic relationships between firms and households are affected.	The management of the national economy is structured vertically (top-down: from the state to firms and households)
The regulation of economic relations is based solely on contractual principles and material interests.	Hierarchical relations (in order of subordination to the lowest level of economic relations) are often built on the basis of economic coercion (taxes, customs duties, etc.)

In addition to political functions, the state also performs economic tasks. The basis of state regulation is a scientific forecast of the country's socio-economic development for a year, medium-term (3-5 years) and long-term (10, 20 years). Such forecasts help to achieve the balance of the national economy, which is determined using national accounts and inter-sectoral balances. Typically, there are three variants of the forecast: - pessimistic (with the smallest indicators); - optimistic (with the highest value of indicators); - baseline (with specific indicators). It is taken as the basis of a state plan that reflects the strategic directions and tasks of the state's economic and social development. Depending on the degree of rigidity of the planned tasks, two types of plans are drawn up: directive (for strict mandatory implementation) - used primarily in state-owned enterprises; indicator (recommended, guiding). Secondly, there are a number of programs that ensure the solution of certain socio-economic tasks. Companies participate in the implementation of state orders by placing them. The state selects firms by conducting appropriate competitions. The third principle: the implementation of a policy of "effective demand" by the state.

Conclusion

Effective public finance management is a key condition for sustainable economic development, ensuring social equality, and balanced management of the state budget. The results of the study show that the use of modern approaches to public finance management, the use of international experience, and the effective allocation of financial resources are of great importance. The sustainability of public finances can be ensured through measures such as making the budget system transparent and effective, optimizing tax policy, and controlling public spending.

In addition, it is necessary to implement administrative reforms in public finance management, provide accurate and timely financial reporting, and strengthen public oversight. The effectiveness of public finance management can be improved through the development of international cooperation and the use of financial technologies.

In conclusion, achievements in the field of public financial management contribute significantly not only to economic growth, but also to the socio-economic development of the

country. In the future, the implementation of advanced approaches in this area and the pursuit of continuous improvement are the main guarantees of the success of public financial management.

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